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**“A STUDY TO DETERMINE THE IMPACT OF BULLYING ON THE
MENTAL HEALTH OF THE SCHOOL AND COLLEGE GOING
STUDENTS IN JAMUHAR, ROTHAS, BIHAR”**

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Abstract

The study to determine the impact of bullying on the mental health of school and college going students in Jamuhar Rothas, Bihar. A quantitative research design was adopted with 50 school and college going students randomized sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire comprising demographic variables, the bullying scale and the mental health Assessment Scale. The finding of the study revealed that 52% of the students experienced moderate bullying, 30% experienced high bullying, 16% reported low bullying and 2% report very high bullying. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.59$) was found between bullying and mental health problems, indicating that higher bullying leads psychological distress.

Title of the study

The study to determine the impact of bullying on the mental health of school and college going students in Jamuhar, Rothas, Bihar.

Objective of the study

1. To assess the prevalence of bullying on the school and the college going students in jamuhar, Rothas, Bihar.
2. To associate the impact of bullying on the mental health of school and college

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going students with their selected social demographic variables.

Summary of major findings

A quantitative research design was adopted with 50 school and college going students randomized sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire comprising demographic variables, the bullying scale and the mental health Assessment Scale. The finding of the study revealed that 52% of the students experienced moderate bullying, 30% experienced high bullying, 16% reported low bullying and 2% report very high bullying. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.59$) was found between bullying and mental health problems, indicating that higher bullying leads psychological distress. and selected variables including: Age, Gender, level of education, type of institution and Family background. The findings indicate that a significant proportion of students are exposed to moderate to the high levels of bullying, which negatively affect their well-being and academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

Bullying is a significant issue that can lead to anxiety, depression, and reduced self-esteem among young individuals. Bullying is a common problem in schools and colleges, affecting students from various backgrounds. It can take physical, verbal, social, and cyber forms, impacting students mental well-being. Exposure to bullying during adolescence can lead to anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Bullying is a common problem in schools and colleges, affecting students from various backgrounds. It can take physical, verbal, social, and cyber forms, impacting students mental wellbeing. Understanding its impact will help in developing effective strategies to promote a safe and supportive educational environment. It can lead to anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem.

Therefore, studying its effects is important to develop strategies for a safe and supportive learning environment.

Statement of the problem

A study to determine the impact of bullying on the mental health of school and child going students in Jamuhar, Rothas Bihar.

Objective

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1. To assess the prevalence of bullying on the school and the college going students in jamuhar, Rothas, Bihar.
2. To associate the impact of bullying on the mental health of school and college going students with their selected demographic variables in jamuhar, Rothas, Bihar.

Methods and Materials

The methodology adopt for the research study. The research methodology is a phase of the study deals with the research design setting, variables, population, sample, sample size, sampling technique and criteria for sample collection, tools and technique for the data collection, content validity of the tools, pilot study and plan for data analysis.

Research Approach

The study was quantitative research approach. This approach is used to systematically examine the impact of bullying on the mental health of school and college going students. A quantitative approach has considered appropriate as its enable the researcher to measure bullying experiences and mental health variables objectively.

Sample

The sample include school and college going students who meet the inclusion 22 criteria. The sample size determined based on feasibility and statistical requirements. A total sample of approximately 50 students selected for the study.

Sampling technique

Simple random sampling technique.

Sample size

The estimated sample size is 50.

Description of the tool

The data is collected using a self-questionnaire, which is consist of the following sections:

Section A: Demographic Data This section include items related to age, gender, class/course, type of institution, and family background.

Section B: Bullying Assessment Scale The Bullying Assessment Scale isa structured self-report questionnaire designed to assess the presence, frequency, and types of bullying experienced by students in educational institutions.

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DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The data collection period for the main study was conducted from the 15th February to 20th February 2026.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics which are frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation and inferential statistics. The association of bullying and socio demographic and clinical variables was determined using chi-square test. The data was presented in the form of tables and graphs. All the data was analyzed by using SPSS software version 27.

Data Analysis

The data analysis is presented under the following sections:

Section A: Description of socio-demographic characteristics of students.

Section B: Assessment of prevalence and forms of bullying.

Section C: Assessment of mental health status (anxiety, depression, stress, self-esteem).

Section D: Comparison of mental health status between bullied and non-bullied students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, bullying has a serious negative impact on the mental health of students in Jamuhar, Rohtas, Bihar. Addressing this issue requires a combined effort from schools, families, and the healthcare system. Early intervention, proper counseling, and continuous awareness can significantly improve students mental well-being and promote a healthy educational environment.

Implications of the Study

Nursing Practice

Nurses can identify early signs of bullying and provide emotional support.

Nursing Education

Awareness programs can be included in the curriculum to educate students about bullying.

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Nursing Administration

Institutions can develop anti-bullying policies and counseling services.

Nursing Research

Further studies can be conducted with larger samples and different settings.

Recommendations

Conduct awareness programs on bullying and mental health. Provide counseling and support services for affected students. Implement strict anti-bullying policies in schools and colleges. Encourage reporting of bullying incidents without fear.

Conduct further research with larger sample size and different populations.

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